

Activated Carbon as an Adsorbent for Basic Yellow Dye. Part III. Intraparticle Diffusion Processes

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Intraparticle diffusion is an important rate controlling step during the removal of Deorlene Yellow 2G dye from effluent using activated carbon. A rate parameter, k , has been defined and used to correlate the variables as a function of the square root of time.

THE mechanism of adsorption involves a study on the diffusional processes through the boundary layer surrounding the particle, adsorption onto the external surface of the particle followed by intraparticle diffusion into the bulk of the adsorbent particle. The surface mass transfer effects were studied in Part II of this work; the longer time based effects of intraparticle diffusion are considered in this section.

Theoretical analysis :

The mathematical theory of diffusion is based on the hypothesis that the rate of transfer of diffusing substance, through unit area of a section, is proportional to the concentration gradient measured normal to the section, i.e., Fick's first law.

$$F = -D \frac{dC}{dx} \quad (1)$$

where F is the rate of transfer per unit area of the section, C is the concentration of diffusing substance, x is the space co-ordinate, and D is the diffusion coefficient.

The fundamental differential equation of diffusion in an isentropic medium where there is a concentration gradient along the x axis is given by Fick's second law.

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = D \frac{d^2C}{dx^2} \quad (2)$$

Other forms of the diffusion equation follow by transformation of co-ordinates, or by considering elements of volume of different shape, for example, cylinders or spheres.

Many molecular adsorption processes involve diffusive mass transport and the interpretation of overall behaviour in terms of 'true' diffusivity and intrinsic equilibrium sorption properties is difficult. A meaningful diffusion coefficient cannot often be derived: the standard procedure of fitting the overall rate behaviour to the classical solution of Fick's equation results in the derivation of apparent diffusion coefficients that often vary with concentration. The mathematical form of Fick's second

equation in terms of spherical polar co-ordinates r , θ and ϕ is given by

$$\frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{1}{r^2} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial r} D r^2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{\sin \phi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} D \sin \theta \frac{\partial C}{\partial \theta} + \frac{D}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial \phi^2} \right\} \quad \dots (3)$$

The solution of the differential equations for unsteady state diffusion has been performed for spheres and have been represented in terms of fraction component adsorbed $(C_0 - C_t)/(C_0 - C_\infty)$ as functions of $(Dt/a^2)^{0.5}$. The model used in this paper assumes (i) the concentration of dyestuff is uniform at C_0 throughout the solution and is zero in the adsorbent particle at the start of diffusion ($t=0$), (ii) diffusion is radial, there being no variation in concentration with angular position and (iii) a surface mass transfer process occurs during the early stages of adsorption. The solution of this model is available^{1,2} and indicates that a plot of the fractional uptake of adsorbate against $(Dt/a^2)^{0.5}$ is linear from around 10-60 percent adsorption. Since the diffusion coefficient D and particle size are constant for any given system, the uptake is linearly dependent on the square root of time. Consequently a rate parameter, k , has been defined as the slope of a graph of the amount of dye adsorbed per gram of adsorbent against $t^{0.5}$. The amount of dye adsorbed, mg, per gram of carbon, X/M , is given by

$$\frac{X}{M} = \frac{C_0 - C_t}{C_0} \times \frac{V}{M} \quad \dots (4)$$

where V is the volume of dye solution, l, and M is the mass of carbon.

Results

(i) *Effect of agitation* : The contact time experiments can be used to establish the time dependence of the system. The normal function of time (t) in diffusion controlled processes is $t^{0.5}$ and Fig. 1 shows a plot of Basic Yellow dye uptake against $t^{0.5}$ for various agitation speeds. The linear

portion of the plots is due to intraparticle diffusion being predominant as the rate-controlling step. As the bulk dye concentration and the surface dye concentration start to decrease, the final portion of the figure begins to curve due to a decrease in the rate of diffusion.

Fig. 1. Plot of Basic Yellow dye adsorbed, X/M mg dye per g carbon, against square root of contact time, $\text{min}^{0.5}$, for various agitation speeds.

The slopes, k values, of Fig. 1 were determined and are listed in Table 1 and a plot of k against \log R.P.M. is shown in Fig. 2 indicating linear variation.

Fig. 2. Plot of rate parameter, k , mg dye g^{-1} carbon $\text{min}^{-0.5}$, against \log R.P.M.

(ii) *Effect of initial dye concentration*: The effect of initial dye concentration with $t^{0.5}$ is shown in Fig. 3. Theoretical equations for intraparticle diffusion indicate that the concentration dependence

TABLE 1—THE EFFECT OF VARIABLES (AGITATION, INITIAL DYE CONCENTRATION, PARTICLE SIZE, TEMPERATURE AND CARBON MASS) ON THE RATE PARAMETER, k , mg, dye per g CARBON $\text{min}^{0.5}$

R.P.M.	150	200	400	500	600
k	2.14	2.50	2.78	3.12	3.35
C_0 mg dm^{-3}	50	100	200	300	400
k	0.42	0.65	2.20	3.00	3.40
dp (mean) μ	302	427	605	780	—
k	4.00	3.10	2.55	2.15	—
$T^\circ\text{K}$	293	313	333	353	—
k	4.00	6.00	9.5	14.0	—
Mg	2.6	3.0	3.4	3.8	4.6
k	1.0	1.6	1.8	2.7	2.9

Fig. 3. Plot of Basic Yellow dye adsorbed, X/M mg dye per g carbon, against square root of contact time, $\text{min}^{0.5}$, for various initial dye concentrations.

of a diffusion-adsorption process will vary depending on the characteristics of the adsorption isotherm on the fraction dye adsorbed at equilibrium. The adsorption of alkylbenzene sulphonates onto activated carbon has been investigated³ and the rate controlling step is shown to be solely dependent on intraparticle diffusion. The same mechanism was postulated as a rate controlling step in the uptake of other solutes by different types of granular adsorbents, including carbon⁴. It seems likely that intraparticle diffusion is important in the adsorption of Basic Yellow dye on carbon.

In the case of intraparticle diffusion only being the rate determining step it was found that k varied with the square root of the initial concentrations used³. The results for Basic Yellow dye and carbon are shown in Fig. 4 which represents a plot of k against initial dye concentration on logarithmic coordinates. The variation is linear but the gradient indicates that k varies with $C_0^{1.15}$. It is apparent that the mechanism of Basic Yellow dye adsorption on carbon is complex involving surface mass transfer and intraparticle diffusion is the rate controlling step. The rate parameters are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 4. Plot of log rate parameter by k mg dye g^{-1} carbon $min^{-0.5}$, against log initial dye concentration, $log C_0$ $mg\ dm^{-3}$.

(iii) *Effect of carbon particle size* : A series of plots of X/M against $t^{0.5}$ are shown in Fig. 5 for a series of different particle size ranges. From the linear portions of the plots the k values were determined and are listed in Table 1. Although the k values do not have the normal dimensions for rates, their relative values for similar conditions should be significant as rate parameters. If the mechanism of uptake is one of adsorption on the external sites

Fig. 5. Plot of Basic Yellow dye adsorbed, X/M mg dye per g carbon, against square root of contact time, $min^{0.5}$, for various particle size ranges.

□ 250 - 355 μ ; ■ 355 - 500 μ ;
 ○ 500 - 710 μ ; ● 710 - 850 μ ;

of a non-porous adsorbent, the rate of adsorption and hence the parameter, k , should vary reciprocally with the first power of the diameter of the carbon particles^{2,3}. This inverse relationship holds also for porous adsorbents when the rate of transport to internal surface areas is controlled by an external resistance, i.e., film transport. Fig. 6 indicates that for Basic Yellow dye adsorption onto carbon, the k values are found to vary reciprocally as some power, n , of the particle diameter. The variation observed is in accord with the equations for intraparticle diffusion given by Crank³ and the power constant $n=0.67$.

Fig. 6. Plot of log rate parameter, $log k$, mg dye g^{-1} carbon $min^{-0.5}$, against log particle diameter.

(iv) *Effect of temperature* : The results of the contact time experiments carried out at temperatures above room temperatures were shown in Part I⁵. The rate parameters were determined as in the previous sections and are listed in Table 1. The rate of dye adsorption is increased as the temperature increases. An increase in temperature accelerates the velocity of adsorption by decreasing the viscosity of the dye solution, increasing the diffusion rate of dye molecules and hastening the displacement of preadsorbed dyes from the pores of the carbon.

The rate parameters were plotted logarithmically against reciprocal Kelvin temperature and Fig. 7 shows the variation is linear. From the gradient an activation energy of 19×10^3 $kJ\ kmol^{-1}$ was determined and the value lies within the expected range for diffusion controlled processes.

(v) *Effect of carbon mass* : The effect of varying the mass of carbon on the rate of dye uptake was studied. The rate parameters were determined and are listed in Table 1 and a plot of $log k$ against log carbon mass, shows linear variation in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7. Plot of log rate parameter against reciprocal absolute temperature.

Fig. 8. Plot of log rate parameter against log mass of adsorbent.

Conclusion

Analysis of the contact time data gives an indication of the mechanism involved in the adsorption of Basic Yellow dye on carbon. Intraparticle diffusion is important in the rate determining step but it is not completely independent of surface mass transfer processes.

Explanation of symbols

a	radial distance, cm, $0 < a < r$
C_t	dye concentration, mg l^{-1}
C_0	concentration in bulk liquid at $t=0$
C_∞	concentration in bulk liquid at equilibrium
d_p	particle diameter
D	diffusivity, $\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
k	rate parameter, $\text{mg dye g}^{-1} \text{ adsorbent min}^{-0.5}$
M	mass of adsorbent, g
n	power constant
r	radius of sphere, cm
t	time, min
x	spacial co-ordinate, cm
X	dye adsorbed, mg
θ and ϕ	polar co-ordinates

Subscripts

O	initial point
t	time
∞	equilibrium

References

1. H. S. CARSLAW and J. C. JAEGER, "Conduction of Heat in Solids", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1947.
2. J. CRANK, "The Mathematics of Diffusion", Clarendon Press, London, 1965.
3. W. J. WEBER and J. C. MORRIS, *J. Sanit. Eng. Div., Amer. Soc. Civ. Engr.*, 1964, 90, 79.
4. F. J. EDESKUTY and N. R. AMUNDSON, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1952, 44, 1968.
5. G. MCKAY, M. S. OTTERBURN and A. G. SWEENEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 58, 963.